

Tool: Sensing Diary

Description	<p>Sensing diaries or Data Journals are used to complement quantitative data (e.g. from Telraam) with rich qualitative data from the citizens. Especially in the context of mobility-related data, it is important to gather as much contextual data as possible (e.g. regarding possible contingency factors that might better explain the hard-sensed data from the sensor). The tool is in the form of a notebook or notepad and includes a calendar. Participants are asked to input any possible information that in their opinion might have affected a specific measure from Telraam – e.g. road closed for works, festival etc.</p>
Why am I doing it?	<p>Enable effective interpretation of the data provided by the sensors.</p>
Resources needed	<p>notebook, pens - it can be done on paper or on digital device</p>
Time needed	<p>Ongoing throughout the duration of the data collection campaign</p>
Skills needed <small>(Not Required, Basic, Intermediate, Advanced)</small>	<p>Subject-matter expertise: Intermediate IT skills: Not Required Facilitation skills: Not Required Event organisation skills: Not Required Project management skills: Not Required Communication skills: Basic</p>
How to use the tool	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Citizens gain awareness from subject matter experts on potential events or other contingency factors that may influence the validity of measures from Telraam. 2. Citizens add annotations to the quantitative data as these contingency factors or other events occur. 3. The process is kept flexible and citizens can use the format (e.g. written form, pictures, videos etc) that suits them the most. 4. The team collects the Data Journals from each participating citizen to enable effective interpretation of the quantitative data.
Outcomes	<p>Sensed data become richer to enable thick descriptions and more in-depth understanding of the phenomenon of interest.</p>
Tips!	<p>Keep reasonable expectations and avoid requesting complex data entries which might frustrate the participants.</p>